

ROLE OF THE METHOD OF ULTRASOUND EXAMINATION OF RENAL BLOOD FLOW IN PATIENTS WITH ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION

Khudoyberdiev Dilshod Karimovich¹

Safarov Ulugbek Khikmatovich²

¹⁻²Bukhara state medical institute.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7407718>

Relevance of the study. Several scientific studies carried out in the last 10 years to identify arterial hypertension and evaluate it, it is considered relevant to carry out a dopplerography examination of the renal arteries in patients with high blood pressure. According to the World Health Organization, in recent years, the number of patients with arterial hypertension has increased by almost 2 times. According to the scientific literature, hypertension associated with kidney diseases was observed in 1.5% of total patients with arterial hypertension.

The purpose of the study. To study the significance of the ultrasound examination method in assessing blood flow in the kidneys in patients with Arterial hypertension.

Material and research methods. A total of 47 patients with Arterial hypertension were examined in the renal arteries. Of those surveyed, 25 (52.2%) were men and 22 (47.8%) women. When determining the hemodynamic indicators of renal blood vessels, the following is important: maximum speed (V_{max}); minimum speed (V_{min}); average speed (V_{med}); pulsation index (P_i); resistance Index (r_i). These checks were carried out on the Mindray DS-60 (China) and SONOSCAPE P9 ultrasound apparatus. Examination in the renal vessels was carried out through a Convex probe (3.5 MHz), in Doppler mode at Vertical and horizontal cuts.

Research results. In our study, the following indicators of hemodynamics of the ultrasound examination were obtained: V_{max} 60.1 ± 1.9 cm/s in the right kidney; V_{min} 33.0 ± 1.4 cm/s; V_{med} 51.3 ± 1.2 cm/s; in the left kidney, 59.9 ± 1.8 cm/s; 32.7 ± 1.1 cm/s; 40.5 ± 1.2 cm/s. The resistance index of the right renal vessels was equal to 0.80 ± 0.01 , the pulsation index was equal to 1.21 ± 0.05 . While the resistance index of the left renal vessels was 0.82 ± 0.01 , the pulsation index was 1.23 ± 0.04 kiymat.

In a group of patients with Arterial hypertension, when the blood flow in the intra-renal blood vessels at the level of the segmental arteries is quantitatively described, the following is determined. The middle of hemodynamic indicators in the right kidney is: - V_{max} 54.3 ± 1.7 cm/s; V_{min} 24.2 ± 1.1 cm/s; while

Vmed was 33.1 ± 1.2 cm/s; in the left kidney, these indicators were, respectively, 54.1 ± 1.9 cm/s; 24.0 ± 1.2 cm/s; equal to 32.8 ± 1.5 cm/s ($r < 0.05$). No significant difference was also found between hemodynamic indicators of intrarenal blood flow in the right and left kidneys.

Conclusion. The data obtained as a result of the examination show that the hemodynamic indicators of the right and left kidneys do not differ sharply from each other, and the average volume value of the left kidney is slightly higher than that of the right kidney. The first exographic signs of kidney damage in patients with Arterial hypertension were analyzed in the ultrasound examination, accompanied by a decrease in hemodynamic indicators of blood flow.

